

Kinetics of Oxidation of Atrolactic Acid by V (v)

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The kinetics of oxidation of Atrolactic acid with V(v) has been studied. The oxidation was found to be of first order with respect to V(v) and to Atrolactic acid. The activation energy, frequency factor and entropy of activation were found to be 15.56 K.Cals, 5.9×10^7 Sec.⁻¹ and -20.18 E.U. The oxidation was found to be acid dependent, the rate increasing with increasing concentration of the acid. This acid dependence was found to be related to $[H_3O^+]$ but not to Hammett's h_0 . Addition of some metal sulphates did not indicate any primary salt effect. The oxidation appeared to proceed through an initial complex formation and subsequently through free radicals. The equilibrium constant for the formation of complex and its rate of decomposition have been calculated.

The first systematic study of the oxidation of various organic substrates like ketones, glycols by quinquevalent vanadium was attempted by Waters and Co-workers¹. In the present investigation the oxidation of an α -hydroxy acid with V(v) has been investigated with a view to find out the effect of an α -methyl group on the rate of oxidation and to suggest a possible course of oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Atrolactic acid was prepared from acetophenone by the standard method². It was crystallised from benzene.

Sodium metavanadate used was of E. Merck quality. A stock solution of it was prepared in standard sulphuric acid solution. The strength was also checked by titrating a known volume of it against standard Mohr's salt solution.

Atrolactic acid solution was prepared in distilled water and its strength was determined by titrating with standard alkali.

Kinetic measurement : Equal volumes (25 ml.) of sodium metavanadate (in aqueous sulphuric acid) and atrolactic acid solution, both of known concentrations were brought to the temperature of the thermostat and then mixed. The course of the reaction was followed by withdrawing 5 ml. portions of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time, chilling by ice to check the reaction and estimating the amount of the unchanged oxidant volumetrically by a standard Mohr's salt solution, using 3 to 5 drops of 0.066 (M) N-phenyl anthranilic acid as an indicator.

1. W. A. Waters and J. S. Littler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1299; 1959, 3014; 1959, 4046; 1960, 2761, 2767.
2. E. L. Eliel and J. P. Freeman, *Org. Synthesis*, 1953, 33, 7.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Dependence of rate on vanadium (v) 10^3 [Atrolactic acid] = 4.2(M); [H⁺] = 0.5(M), Temp = 30°

[V(v)] × 10 ³ (M)	1.04	1.93	3.0	4.0	5.0
$k \times 10^4$ in Sec. ⁻¹	4.50	4.211	4.53	4.79	4.62

TABLE II

Dependence of rate on the concentration of the organic substrate 10^3 [V(v)] = 1.0(M); [H⁺] = 0.5(M); Temp = 30°

[ALA] × 10 ³ (M)	1.05	2.10	3.15	4.20
$k \times 10^4$ in Sec. ⁻¹	1.16	2.02	2.97	4.50
$k/[ALA] \times 10^2$ mole ⁻¹ litre sec. ⁻¹	11.05	12.12	11.86	10.72

TABLE III

Dependence of rate on acidity 10^3 [V(v)] = 5.0(M); 10^3 [ALA] = 4.33(M); Temp. = 30°

[H ⁺] (M)	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50	0.75	1.0	1.8
$k \times 10^4$ in Sec. ⁻¹	3.45	3.67	3.784	4.645	5.73	6.2	8.33

TABLE IV

Influence of temperature on reaction velocity 10^3 [V(v)] = 5.0(M); 10^3 [ALA] = 4.33(M); [H⁺] = 0.25(M)

Temperature in °C	$k \times 10^4$ in Sec. ⁻¹
25	2.346
30	3.672
35	5.476

TABLE V

Effect of salts on the rate of oxidation 10^3 [V(v)] = 5.0(M); 10^3 [ALA] = 4.33(M); [H⁺] = 0.25(M); Temp = 30°

Nature of salt	[salt] × 10 ³ (M)	$k \times 10^4$ in Sec. ⁻¹
Nil	0	3.672
KCl	2.535	8.608
K ₂ SO ₄	2.535	3.505
MgSO ₄	2.535	3.725

DISCUSSION

The rate data have been expressed as the pseudo unimolecular rate constants k obtained from the slope of the graph of $\log [V(v)]$ against time. Fairly constant values are obtained when these rate data are divided by the atrolactic acid concentration as given in Table II.

Influence of temperature on reaction velocity: The reaction velocities were measured at three different temperatures and are presented in Table IV. The Arrhenius equation was found to be valid in the temperature range studied. The energy of activation was calculated from the slope of the straight line plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$. The values of the energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation were found to be 15.56 K.Cals, $5.9 \times 10^7 \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$ and -20.18 E.U. respectively. The frequency factor for unimolecular decomposition processes is usually observed to be more than $10^{10} \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$. The low value of the frequency factor observed in the present investigation suggests that the activated complex is more rigid than the initial state. This is also evident from the negative value of the entropy of activation. This further suggests that a free radical may be involved in the reaction mechanism.

Dependence on acid: The rate of reaction has been found to increase with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion. Table III shows that the rate of reaction varies with hydrogen ion concentration. A plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [H^+]$ did not pass through the origin indicating that VO^+_2 is also an oxidising species in the oxidation of atrolactic acid. It is also observed that the rate value beyond an acid concentration of $0.5(M)$ increases more rapidly than is expected. This increase in rate may be ascribed to the occurrence of a more stronger oxidising species than VO^+_2 , formed by rapid equilibrium

This equilibrium explains satisfactorily that the acid dependence is on $[H_3O^+]$ and not on Hammett's h_0 , as would probably be the case with a cation $VO.OH^{++}$, that did not incorporate a molecule of water.

The same conclusion has also been obtained by Littler and Waters¹ in the oxidation of monohydric alcohols and by Mullick *et al.*³ in the oxidation of lactic acid by vanadic acid.

Influence of salt on reaction velocity: Different salts i.e., K_2SO_4 , $MgSO_4$ and KCl were added to the reaction mixture. The results in Table V show that there is no primary salt effect. Since addition of sulphate ion did not cause any considerable influence on the rate of oxidation, the possibility of the formation of a sulphato complex by the reaction between trihydroxy pervanadyl ion and bisulphate ion by the equilibrium

can be ruled out. Since no primary salt effect was observed, it was not felt necessary to maintain constant ionic strength.

Stoichiometry of the oxidation : Two moles of vanadium (v) were found to be absorbed per mole of atrolactic acid. Carbon dioxide was evolved and acetophenone was obtained as the product of reaction as characterised by preparing its 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazone.

Hence, the stoichiometric equation for its oxidation can be represented as :

Mechanism : This reaction could proceed either by termolecular collision or by separate consecutive stages, (a) reduction of one vanadium (v) ion and production of a univalent radical or ion from the hydroxy acid, and (b) the quick oxidation of the radical (ion) to acetophenone by a second vanadium (v) ion. That this oxidation involves free radical has been confirmed by mercuric chloride reduction test⁴. Stage (a) is preceded by a reversible formation of a complex between the oxidising species and atrolactic acid, which then undergoes slower first order decomposition into vanadium (iv) and the radical by a relayed one electron switch. No kinetic evidence however, for the initial complex formation between the vanadium and the α -hydroxy acid could be discerned in contrast to the oxidation effected by manganic pyrophosphate⁵. But this is not surprising since oxidation of cyclohexanol⁶ by vanadium (v) in which complex formation is involved, shows no deviation from first order kinetics with respect to alcohol.

So the foregoing discussion suggests the following mechanism :

4. A. Y. Drummond and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2836.
5. P. Levesley and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217,
6. J. S. Littler and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4046

Hence, the reaction will obey the following equation based on the theory of Duke⁷.

$$\frac{-d[V(v)]}{dt} = \frac{k'K[ALA][V(v)]}{1+K[ALA]}$$

where k' is the rate of decomposition of the complex and K is the equilibrium constant between the reactants and the complex.

But
$$\frac{-d[V(v)]}{dt} = k[V(v)]$$

where k is the observed rate constant.

So by substituting this value and rearranging, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k'K[ALA]} = \frac{1}{k'}$$

A straight line plot was obtained when $1/k$ was plotted against $1/[ALA]$, from the intercept and slope of which the rate of decomposition of the complex and the equilibrium constant values were obtained respectively. The values were $14.29 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ and $8.4 \times 10^1 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ litre}$ respectively.

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7. F. R. Duke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2885, 3054.